

Key Profile Components for Computer Scientists

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1. Introduction and Scope

This report provides an overview of a broad set of components that are relevant to academic profiles of researchers in the field of Computer Science (CS). Each component corresponds to a specific type of *research activity* or *career achievement* which can be supplemented with *valuable context* (which enriches the basic set of metadata related to the activity/achievement) and can be confirmed or validated through *tangible evidence*¹. The aforementioned activities can be classified into broad *categories*, which provide a structured framework to represent the diverse contributions of CS researchers. The report is shaped following a similar structure.

The main objective of the report is to give inspiration for academic profile templates and platforms by outlining the key components that could be supported in order to effectively summarise the careers of researchers in CS. At the same time, the report seeks to inform research assessment processes by highlighting the wide range of activities in which CS researchers engage, encouraging greater recognition of this diversity. However, the report does not aim to offer prescriptive recommendations on how research assessment should be conducted or which aspects should be prioritised, acknowledging that such decisions require more complex, content-specific designs that take into account institutional and other considerations. Finally, it should be noted that providing a comprehensive list of all possible contexts or forms of evidence for each activity or achievement was beyond the scope of this report. The lists included are intended to be indicative rather than exhaustive.

¹ The specific means of confirmation or validation that provide formal proof of a given activity or achievement is out of the scope of the current report. For instance, participation in a program committee of a conference is considered tangible evidence of a researcher's community service (see Section 2.3.1.). Such evidence might be demonstrated through a published conference program committee listing or a peer-review certification. However, a detailed discussion of these validation mechanisms lies beyond the scope of this report.

2. Overview of Key Profile Components

2.1. Activities related to Research Outputs

This category encompasses all activities through which researchers produce and share scholarly outputs that advance knowledge in their field. These include the publication of research articles, datasets, and software, as well as other forms of research products, like research grant proposals and peer review reports.

2.1.1. Publication-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles (e.g., based on CRedT) - Affiliation information - Access information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preprints and postprints - Journal articles - Conference and workshop articles (including demo and poster papers) - Books and book chapters - Technical reports

2.1.2. Data-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles (e.g., curation) - Affiliation information - Access information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Datasets - Database records

2.1.3. Software-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles (e.g., development, documentation) - Affiliation information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Code - Software packages - Documentation

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators 	
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2.1.4. Activities Related to Peer Review

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Affiliation information - Access information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer review reports

2.1.5. Activities Related to Grant Proposal Writing

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles (e.g., coordinator, WP leader) - Affiliation information - Access information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Acceptance status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grant proposal documents

2.1.6. Activities Related to Other Types of Research Products

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles - Affiliation information - Access information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ML models <open ended>

2.2. Dissemination

This category encompasses all activities through which researchers disseminate their work, both within the scientific community and to the broader public. These activities include invited talks and poster presentations at scientific conferences and events, as well as contributions to mass media and social platforms (e.g., blog posts, public lectures, media interviews, podcasts, and similar forms of outreach).

2.2.1. Event-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles - Affiliation information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators (e.g., number of attendees) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posters - Invited talks - Participation to panel discussions - Tutorials

2.2.2. Media-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution roles - Affiliation information - Researcher-provided fields and keywords - Researcher-provided connections with other outputs - Researcher-provided summaries and narratives - Impact and usage indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Blog posts - Public videos (webinars, interviews, etc.) - Podcasts - Mentions in news articles

2.3. Community Service

This category encompasses all activities through which researchers contribute their expertise in service roles, both to the research community and to society at large. Such activities include serving on conference or workshop organizing and program committees, participating in the editorial boards of journals, and in expert panels or advisory boards.

2.3.1. Service in Conferences/Workshops

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Related track (e.g., research, demo, industry) - Affiliation information - Period of service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation in Program Committees - Participation in Organisation Committee - Other roles (e.g., proceeding chairs, awards committees, session chairs etc)

2.3.2. Service in Journals

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service - Type of involvement (e.g., special issue editor) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation in editorial boards

2.3.3. Expert Advisory Work

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grant review report - Organisation review report - Investigation report - Advisory board report - Policy brief - Specification - Participation in work/focus/interest group listing

2.4. Education

This category covers all activities through which researchers contribute to education and capacity building by sharing their knowledge and expertise. These include academic teaching at undergraduate and postgraduate levels, the design and delivery of training activities such as seminars, workshops, or webinars, and the supervision and mentoring of doctoral, master's, and bachelor's students.

2.4.1. Academic Teaching

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service - Department and university 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Course teaching - Archived teaching material (e.g., slides,

	videos) - MOOC organisation
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2.4.2. Training Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
-	- Archived training material (e.g., slides, videos)

2.4.3. Supervision

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
- Department and university	- Theses and dissertations (PhD, MSc, BSc) with the researcher as supervisor/advisor - Published co-authored papers

2.5. Activities related to Innovation and Industry

This category encompasses activities through which researchers contribute to innovation and the transfer of knowledge beyond academia. Such activities include the creation and registration of patents, the establishment of new companies or active participation in existing ones in leadership or advisory roles, and the development of products or services with commercial value.

2.5.1. Patent-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
- Contribution role	- Registered patents

2.5.2. Company-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
- Contribution role / position - Company financial information	- Official role in a company

2.5.3. Product-related Activities

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribution role - Product financial information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product or service with commercial value

2.6. Leadership

This category includes activities through which researchers take on leadership roles that shape and guide the direction of research, organizations, and initiatives. These may involve holding leadership positions in academic or professional organizations, such as serving as directors, deans, or board members; leading research grants as principal investigators or coordinators; and undertaking other roles that require strategic vision, responsibility, and coordination.

2.6.1. Leadership in Organisations

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Team leadership - Unit management (e.g., president, director)

2.6.2. Leadership in Grants

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project management - Project coordination - Work package leader - Task leader

2.6.3. Other Leadership Roles

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Period of service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leading role in scientific societies - Leading role in working, focus, or interest groups

2.7. Career Achievements

This category highlights significant career milestones and recognitions that reflect the long-term impact and excellence of a researcher's work. These may include research-related

achievements such as landmark publications, global recognition through prestigious awards and honors, and distinguished appointments or fellowships in leading professional bodies.

2.7.1. Research-related Achievements

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
-	- Article awards (e.g., best paper, test of time, etc.)

2.7.2. Global Recognition

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
-	- Global recognition awards

2.7.3. Other Achievements

Valuable Context	Tangible Evidence
-	- Fellowships (e.g., ACM fellow, IEEE fellow)

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